

MAHMUDHOJA BEHBUDI'S VIEWS ON RELIGIOUS AND SECULAR HARMONY

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Abstract. The article compares Mahmudhoja Behbudi's views on the need to achieve the balance between religiosity and secularism, and his contributions to the development of religion and enlightenment. Also, the article describes Mahmudhoja Behbudi's services to protect Islam from various superstitions and advance knowledge.

Keywords. Religion, religious belief, sharia, jurisprudence, Muslim, religiosity, secularism, Jadidism, enlightenment.

In today's era of globalization, threats such as attempts to undermine the balance of religion and secularism is expanding. In particular, dividing science into religious and secular, contrasting religion and secularism creates the ground for the emergence of groups under the guise of religion and the negative impact of ideas of immorality on the minds of young people. Therefore, in the analysis of religious and secular trends today, it is important to turn to the life and work of Mahmudhoja Behbudi, the founder of the modernist movement, a religious and public figure, who is considered one of the enlighteners of Turkestan.

In fact, Mahmudhoja Behbudi paid special attention to ensuring the harmony of religion and secularism and to the development of religion and science during his creative career. He received religious education in Samarkand and Bukhara madrasas, and because he had the ability to analyze and apply the sources of Sharia perfectly, he later rose to the rank of qazi and mufti.

During his career as a mufti, Mahmudhoja Behbudi always tried to protect the Islamic religion from various superstitions, to give refutations against bigots based on Sharia sources, and to ease the burden of the people. He also published social and scientific articles in the press, which caused the people to increase their religious and worldly knowledge. He studied the sources of Shari'ah thoroughly and used them in his work by comparing the ratio of religiosity and secularism. His mastery of religious knowledge was also demonstrated in his mufti work. This is confirmed by the story of Nusrat Rahmat, a well-known journalist, writer, and promoter of Mahmudhoja Behbudi's work and heritage from Uzbekistan. According to the incident: "... there was a horse thief in Jomboy. He crossed the Bakhmal Mountains, stole horses from the villages of Panjikent, and sold the stolen horses to the Samarkand market. But he does not commit such criminal acts in the place where he lives. One day, the horse he was stealing got out of control and did not walk when he told him to go, killing the thief. At that moment, he saw a white horse tied in a stable. Boyagi ties his hairpin instead, rides a white horse, and leaves it at the house of a village acquaintance in Tagitepa, near Samarkand. But the crime is discovered, and after a long investigation, the judge gives a sentence to cut off the hand of the thief. But Behbudi, as the mufti of Jombay, objects to the judge issuing such a terrible sentence."

"Maybe you don't know." Recently, this punishment was canceled, - he says as he lies in bed.

Realizing that the annulment of the sentence could cast a shadow on his reputation, the judge opened and read the 38th verse of the Qur'an's Surah "Moida". And in this verse: "Cut off the hands of the male thief and the female thief - as a punishment according to their deeds and as a punishment from God!" The words [1] are written.

- Can they cancel it? - asks the judge.

If a thief's hands are cut off, first, his reputation in the neighborhood and among his relatives will not only be lost, but he will face their anger and hatred. Considering that he may stay, he wants the punishment to be lighter and shows the judge verse 96 of the Qur'an "Nisa" and says: "Allah is Forgiving and Merciful" [2].

After these words of Qazi Behbudi, he agrees to cancel the sentence" [3].

As seen from the incident, Behbudi knew Islam well and was a person rich in religious and philosophical observation. We have also known him as an expert in the sciences of jurisprudence, hadith and tafsir, who were able to use Shariah evidence wisely in his mufti work. The fact that he was able to use and teach others the proofs of the goodness of Islam at the right time proves that he was an incomparable scholar.

Literary scholar Salih Kasimov in his article entitled "Behbudi and Jadidchilik" informs: "...none of the jurists - scholars of religious knowledge of his time - could match Behbudi in terms of the breadth of fiqh science. However, the difference and advantage of Behbudi from some reactionary clerics were that he never interpreted any rule or guidance of fiqh in a way that harmed the people's interests and social progress. On the contrary, relying on verses and hadiths, he protected the interests of workers and issued fatwas calling for the development of friendly relations with Europeans who called for knowledge and enlightenment" [4].

During his life, Mufti Mahmudhoja Behbudi, as a scholar who acquired both religious and secular sciences, tried to make others know and improve the economic and social condition of the people. In his article entitled "Address to the Youth": "...Islam is such a mature and progressive religion that no matter how modern the knowledge is, a person's belief in the religion of Islam will be strong. For example, it is known to journalists that many of the most famous European scholars are Muslims. So, the reason is that his science is useful instead of harming modern Islam, now let's come to matlab" [5], we can see from his thoughts that he tried to ensure the commonality between religion and secularism.

For example, Behbudi wants to emphasize that the more knowledge one acquires, the stronger a person's religious faith will be, and that worldly knowledge will serve the development of Islam, rather than sinking it into the mire of decline. He also cites the following words as proof of his words: "Dear brothers! Hazrat Ali effendi karramallahu wajhahu says: "Allimu avladakum li zaman ghairi zamanikum, liannahum khuliqu li zaman ghairi zamanikum". Content: "O Muslims! Teach your children science! Because God Almighty made them a people, except for your time, that is, for the time to come. The above word is such a valuable and useful and necessary word that if only we, Muslims, were a factor with it, the whole world and the hereafter would be prosperous" [6]. In this place, he said: "If we don't know Arabic, the world will be lost if we don't know Arabic" [7], "We don't want to make the people Russian and unfriendly, and we don't want to ruin the religion of Islam, but we want our honorable people to develop our religion materially, and we want to live in Russia, sticking to our noble religion." [8] - also shows that acquiring worldly knowledge does not mean renouncing religion, but keeping up with the times. In order not to fall behind the times, it shows the need to acquire worldly knowledge and progress without giving up one's religion.

Mahmudhoja Behbudi's opinion: "Let the children have a scientific, religious and scientific modern inheritance from their fathers" [9] also sounds like it is a very important necessity to achieve the harmony of religion and worldliness. Mahmudhoja Behbudi's thoughts of a century ago are still relevant for today and serve as an important ideological basis for ensuring the balance of religious and secular trends.

In conclusion, Mahmudhoja Behbudi paid great attention to the issues of religion, faith, knowledge and enlightenment during his life. Behbudi was an ardent propagandist who mobilized all his strength to preserve the religion and make the next generation literate. Also, the activity of Mahmudhoja Behbudi in the religious and educational sphere showed Islam is not a religion against secularism, but it is a

source of spirituality that reveals the spiritual aspect of worldly affairs and regulates it. After all, if religion is understood through science, it will be possible to respond with enlightenment against destructive ideas spread by groups under the guise of religion in today's dangerous times. Therefore, the services of Mahmudhoja Behbudi in the path of religion and knowledge, drawing correct conclusions from his practical actions, serve as an example school for the youth of today.

References

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